

An In- Vitro Study to Compare The Effect of Amphotericin B & Clove Oil in Growth of Candida Albicans by Incorporating It in Heat Cure Denture Base Resin

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Abstract

Dentures made from acrylic resin based polymeric systems are popular because of their ease of moulding, excellent esthetics and suitable mechanical characteristics in most clinical conditions. However, these denture bases are easily colonized by oral microorganisms which can induce a chronic inflammatory response in the oral mucosa, described as denture stomatitis. So in this study amphotericin B and clove oil is added to heat cure denture base resin so as to prevent denture induced stomatitis among denture wearers.

Materials Methods: Amphotericin B and clove oil is added to 20 heat cure denture base resin to evaluate the growth of candida albicans.

Results and Conclusion: In the present study, significant difference was found in the growth of candida albicans.

Keywords: Denture stomatitis, Candida Albicans Growth.

Introduction

The primary etiological factor for denture stomatitis is associated with the growth of Candida species on the fitting surface of the denture where there is less flow of saliva resulting in anaerobic conditions and decrease in pH. Other factors such as poor denture hygiene, continuous denture wearing, ill-fitting dentures, the amount of tissue covered by dentures, wearing denture at night, smoking, carbohydrate-rich diet and allergy to denture base material may also lead to denture stomatitis.^[1]

The treatment for Candidiasis includes denture replacement, adoption of prophylactic measures by the patient and prescription of antifungal drugs. For elderly and institutionalized patients this treatment is further complicated because of factors such as loss of memory, difficulty in proper cleaning of the denture and following a strict routine of topical application of an antifungal agent. These limitations have encouraged the development of other methods of drug delivery, such as incorporation of antifungal agents into denture base materials. The rationale for the development of such material is to ensure delivery of antifungal agents at the site of action within minimum possible concentration. This paper discusses the types of antifungal agents incorporated into the denture base materials in order to prevent denture stomatitis.^[2]

Denture stomatitis is more commonly seen in the maxillary mucosa. The prevalence of denture stomatitis is varied from 15 to 65% and even more significant in the

institutionalized denture wearing population at up to 72%. This condition is usually asymptomatic, although it can be associated with burning, bleeding and unpleasant taste. Even though several microorganisms can cause this condition, most studies showed that Candida albicans and the ill fitting dentures promote the development of this condition.^[3]

Candida albicans is an oral commensally fungus found in 40% of human beings, which facilitates the formation of denture plaque, in which Candida albicans. Candida albicans is asexual diploid fungus. It reproduces by budding and produces pseudohyphae both in culture and in tissues. It may be found in yeast form (blastospore) or mycelial form (pseudohyphae). Yeast form is found in denture wearers with normal mucosa while mycelial form is seen in denture stomatitis patients. Like other yeasts, Candida albicans is gram positive. The management of Candida associated denture stomatitis is complex due to its multifactorial etiology.^[4]

Current treatment includes following options: Meticulous oral and denture hygiene, removal of dentures at night or prolonged rest periods, antifungal therapy such as fluconazole and topical nystatin etc., correction of minor denture faults and tissue conditioners application on the fitting surface of the denture etc. The present study

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compared efficacy of Amphotericin and Clove oil incorporated into heat cure acrylic denture base resin as drug delivery method for Denture stomatitis.^[5]

Amphotericin B (AmB), as one of the polyene group elements, and clotrimazole (CT), as one of the azole group elements, are usually used in a different pharmaceutical formula such as solution, cream, ointment, jelly, tissue conditioner, or lozenge for the treatment of oral candidiasis or denture stomatitis.^[6]

Antifungal properties of some essential oils have been well documented. Clove oil is reported to have strong antifungal activity against many fungal species.^[7]

The use of plant derived products as diseases control agents have been studied, since they tend to have low mammalian toxicity, less environmental effects and wide public acceptance. Essential oils have a long history of use as natural microbial agents and have recently been used in a number of pharmaceutical, food, and cosmetic products since these oils effectively inhibit the growth of a wide range of microorganisms, with fewer side effects than synthetic.^[8]

Clove oil was found to possess strong antifungal activity against opportunistic fungal pathogens such as *Candida albicans*, *Cryptococcus neoformans* and *Aspergillus fumigatus*. The essential ingredient responsible for its antifungal activity is eugenol from the clove. Eugenol is the main volatile compound of extracted oil from clove bud (*S. aromaticum* L.) that is used in traditional medicine, as a bactericide, fungicide, anesthetic, and others. However, its antimicrobial activity was found to be higher against fungi than against bacteria. Besides eugenol (49–87 %), clove oil also contains β -caryophyllene (4–21 %), eugenyl acetate (0.5– 21 %), smaller amounts of α -humulene along with trace amounts.^[9]

Aim & Objectives

Aim: The purpose of the study is to treat or prevent to a greater extent the growth of biofilms of *Candida albicans* associated denture stomatitis by incorporating Amphotericin B and Clove oil in heat cure denture base resin.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To evaluate the effect of heat cure denture base resin in preventing the growth of biofilms of *Candida albicans* by keeping the concentration of monomer as 7ml, concentration of Amphotericin B as 2.4ml and the concentration of clove oil as 1.2ml.
2. To evaluate the effect of heat cure denture base resin in preventing the growth of biofilms of *Candida albicans* by keeping the concentration of monomer as 7ml, but increasing the concentration of Amphotericin B to 4.8ml and keeping the concentration of clove oil as 1.2ml.
3. To evaluate the effect of heat cure denture base resin in preventing the growth of biofilms of *Candida albicans* by not incorporating any drug (neither Amphotericin B nor Clove oil) and keeping the concentration of monomer as 7ml.

Materials & Method

Chemicals used

- Amphotericin B
 - Clove oil
 - Heat cure acrylic resin (monomer and polymer)
 - Sabouraud's dextrose agar (SDA)
 - Sabouraud's dextrose broth (SDB)
- AmB and Clove oil were purchased from Maa

Pharmaceuticals, Bhubaneswar (Odisha). Polymer powder and monomer solution were purchased from Vertex-Dental, prosthetic dental products, (Netherlands). Sabouraud's dextrose agar (SDA) and Sabouraud's dextrose broth (SDB) were purchased from (Mast Group, Ltd., UK).

Specimen Preparation

Eighteen PMMA specimens (10 mm × 10 mm × 2 mm) were prepared from a heat-cured acrylic resin denture base. The specimens were divided into 3 groups with 6 specimens in each group. The first group was prepared by adding 2.4ml concentration of AmB and 1.2ml of Clove oil to 7ml of monomer before mixing with polymer powder. The second group was prepared by adding 4.8ml concentration of AmB and 1.2ml of Clove oil to 7ml of monomer before mixing with polymer powder.

The third group was processed without any drug to consider it as a control. The mixing ratio and conditions for processing and polymerization recommended by the manufacturers were strictly followed. The required specimen size of heat-cured acrylic denture base resin was first prepared by cutting the elastic foil of 2-mm thickness into plastic specimens of 10 mm × 10 mm × 2 mm. Flasking and packing were done by the conventional methods. Packing was accomplished according to the manufacturer's instructions. According to the American National Standard/American Dental Association, curing of the heat-cured acrylic resin specimens was carried out by placing the clamped flask in a thermostatically controlled water bath for 90 min at 74°C, and then 60 min at 100°C. Flasks were allowed to cool at room temperature after curing. The acrylic specimens were removed from their stone molds. Any flashes of excess resin material were removed from the specimens using acrylic bur, finished with stone bur, and polished with pumice. The specimens were stored in distilled water (DW) at 37°C for 48 h for conditioning. All the prepared specimens were sterilized by autoclaving at 121°C with 15 bars for 15 min.

Biofilm Formation

C. albicans was obtained from the microbial bank of the Central Public Health Laboratory of Karbala. Biofilm was induced on the PMMA specimens as mentioned by Dhaleet al. with some modifications including denture use. Briefly, *C. albicans* grown on SDA were activated by inoculating in SDB supplied with 8% glucose and incubated at 37°C for 24 h. Growth density of approximately 1.5×10^8 cells of *C. albicans* in each milliliter of sterilized normal saline was obtained after matching with the 0.5 McFarland standard. The PMMA specimens were singly distributed in a sterile screw vial, with three replicates for each type of specimen. Each vial received 2 ml of SDB and 0.1 ml of standardized yeast solution. Mixtures were agitated at 130 rpm for 1 h to stimulate adhesion, followed by incubation at 37°C for 24 h. After incubation, the inoculated PMMA specimens were washed three times with 1 ml of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) to remove nonbiofilm forming cells. Determination of biofilm formation was performed by two assays: crystal violet staining and transmission assays.

Crystal Violet Staining

Total count of *C. albicans* in the form of biofilm was determined by the processing of crystal violet staining as described by Melo et al. with some modifications including denture use. Briefly, after washing of specimens with PBS solution, they were left at room temperature to dry for 45 min.

Dry specimens were stained by submerging in 2 ml of 0.4% aqueous crystal violet solution for 45 min. Then, specimens were washed three times with 1 ml of sterilized DW and destained with 2 ml of 95% ethanol for 45 min. Absorption of destaining solution was measured with a spectrophotometer (APEL, PD-303 UV, Japan) at 595 nm.

Transmission Assay

After the incubation period, each washed PMMA specimen was immediately added to a vial with 2 ml of sterilized normal saline for measurement of percent transmittance (%T) at a wavelength of 405 nm as mentioned by Tumbarello et al. The %T value for each specimen was subtracted from the %T value for the reagent blank to obtain a measure of the amount of light blocked when passing through destaining solution (%T block).

Results

Investigation for antifungal activity of AmB and Clove oil against *C. albicans* after incorporation into heat cure denture base material showed promising results. Low concentration of Amphotericin B revealed a significant ability to reduce the biofilm formation by *C. albicans* as indicated by an absorption value of stained specimens with crystal violet. On comparison of absorption values, less biofilm formed as indicated by the high percentage of transmission was noted under the effect of high concentration of Amphotericin B. However, both assays showed that AmB and Clove oil in different concentrations have inhibitory activity against the development of *C. albicans* biofilms in comparison to PMMA specimens without any agents. The second group having AmB concentration (4.8ml), showed more inhibitory effects on *C. albicans* than the first group having AmB concentration (2.4ml).

Discussion

A novel treatment approach was tested in the present study with the addition of Amphotericin B and Clove Oil powder to denture base materials. Its effectiveness against the adherence of *C. albicans* to the denture base materials was then tested. The results showed that the mean number of *C. albicans* colonies in the tested groups decreased significantly when compared with the conventional heat-polymerized PMMA. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that the amount of *C. albicans* adhering to the PMMA plus Amphotericin B and Clove Oil denture materials would not be different from the amount adhering to the conventional heat-polymerized PMMA was rejected. The slide counting method and direct culture method results, which indicated that the Clove oil and Amphotericin B had positive antifungal effects against *C. albicans* adhesion to the heat-polymerized acrylic resin. One previous study reported that because Amphotericin B and Clove Oil includes the chemical constituents of alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids and tannins it has the ability to prevent microbial infections specifically because of its antimicrobial biological activities. The ability to create a complex with the bacterial cell walls can be seen in these chemicals, which demonstrates their antibacterial activity. Because of the antimicrobial effects of Amphotericin B and Clove Oil powder, it has been used as an active ingredient in many toothpastes and tooth powders.

Conclusion

Within the limitations of this study, it can be concluded that Amphotericin b And Clove Oil exhibits antifungal activity by decreasing the adhesion of *C. albicans* to denture base materials. PMMA acrylic resin modified with Amphotericin B

and Clove oil could be used for the fabrication of removable prostheses as a possible DS treatment or prevention method. However, further investigations of the physical and mechanical results of adding Clove Oil to denture base materials are required.

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